

blending, especially when deoiled neem cake is used. When that mixture is used, the neem cake-urea blend may be applied in a single dose, also saving the cost of topdressing. This is more practical in situations where effective topdressing is not easily done, as in coastal districts of North and South Canara where water management is a problem.

Neem cake obtained from a country press generally contains an average 2% nitrogen, 14% crude fat, 1.2% total calcium oxide, and 0.21% total P₂O₅. The effectiveness of neem cake results from an alkaloid content, such as "Nimbidin," which helps to regulate mineralization and minimize nitrogen losses.

Experiments on the efficacy of neem cake-blended urea in transplanted rice were conducted over four seasons at Mandya centre (see table). The soil type of the experimental site was red sandy

Grain yield and uptake of nitrogen and phosphorus in grain using neem cake-blended urea.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Yield response (kg grain/kg N)	Nitrogen content in grain (%)	Phosphorus content in grain (%)
Neem cake-blended urea using coal tar and kerosene oil, at 80 kg N/ha, all basal	5.2	32	1.4	0.8
Neem cake-blended urea alone, in 2 splits, at 80 kg N/ha	4.7	26	1.3	0.8
Ordinary urea in splits (3) at 100 kg N/ha, recommended practice	4.2	12	1.1	0.7
Control - no nitrogen	2.6	-	0.7	0.5
F Test	**			
C.D. (0.05)	0.4			
C.V. (%)	8.9			

loam (Alfisols) with pH 6.8, less than 0.2 mmho total soluble salts/cm, 0.6% organic carbon, 19.2 kg available phosphorus/ha, and 268.3 kg potassium/ha. All recommended practices were followed. The results indicate that blending

urea with neem cake saved nitrogen fertilizer to the extent of 20% and increased yield up to 15%.

The additional cost for preparing neem cake-blended urea was about US\$5/ha for ingredients and labor. ■

Role of higher nitrogen rate, sulfur, and zinc application in bridging the yield gap of farmer's boro rice in Bangladesh

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Boro rice (transplanted Dec-Jan, harvested Apr-May) usually gives the highest yield per hectare of all the types of rice grown in Bangladesh. The crop is irrigated and farmers generally apply to it a higher intensity management, including fertilizer, than that for aus, transplanted aman, and deepwater rice.

In many cases, however, farmers do not apply adequate amounts of fertilizer to the boro crop. This ultimately reduces yields. Furthermore, in many boro rice-growing areas, soil problems are increasingly evident, particularly because of the continuous wet conditions of the soil in the irrigation projects.

At the BRRI cropping systems research site at Salna, sulfur (S) and zinc (Zn) deficiencies recently were detected. A complete factorial trial with three replications was conducted in 1979-80 in a farmer's field to determine the effect of a higher rate of N, and application of S

Effect of higher rate of N, S, and Zn application on the yield of BR3 boro rice, 1979-80 boro season, Salna village, Dacca, Bangladesh.

Fertilizer rate		Zn (%) used in ZnO suspension in water for root dipping	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Panicles (no./hill) ^a	Plant ht(cm) at harvest ^a	Straw yield ^b (t/ha)
Kg N/ha	Kg S/ha					
40	None	None	3.80 e	8.9 d	73 b	5.1 c
40	None	1.6	3.87 e	8.9 d	73 b	5.4 bc
40	11.3	None	4.35 d	9.3 cd	78 a	5.9 abc
40	11.3	1.6	4.43 cd	9.7 bcd	76 a	5.6 bc
80	None	None	4.54 bcd	10.4 bc	77 a	5.9 abc
80	None	1.6	4.85 abc	11.1 b	78 a	6.5 abc
80	11.3	None	4.92 ab	12.5 a	79 a	6.8 a
80	11.3	1.6	5.09 a	13.2a	80 a	6.9 a

^a In the column, values having a common letter do not differ significantly at the 1% level of significance. ^b In the column, values having a common letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level of significance.

and Zn, on the grain yield of BR3 variety. Ammonium sulfate was the source of S, and the treatment consisted of dipping seedling roots in 2% ZnO suspension in water before transplanting.

The results indicate that a rate of 80 kg N/ha gave a significantly higher grain yield than the farmer's rate of 40 kg N/ha (see table). At the farmer's N level, the Zn treatment did not significantly influence grain yield, but S application increased it. At both levels of N, application of S with or without Zn gave statistically similar grain yields.

But in all cases the Zn treatment gave some quantitative increase in grain yield. The yield gap was 1.3 t/ha, and the contributions of higher N, S, and Zn in bridging the gap were 0.70 (53%), 0.45 (34%), and 0.18 (13%) t/ha.

The number of panicles per hill, plant height, and straw yield also were influenced significantly by the treatments (see table). Results of the present experiment indicate that a higher rate of N and application of S are important for obtaining the potential yield of boro rice at this site. ■